

Effects of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Social Learning Therapy in Reducing Adolescents' Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Oyo Town

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15868217>

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Social Learning Therapy in reducing adolescents' aggressive behaviour among senior secondary schools in Oyo Town. Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest control group design was adopted. The population of the study consisted all senior secondary school adolescents in the study area. Sample of hundred and fifty adolescents were purposively chosen from three Senior Secondary schools in Oyo Town. There were two experimental treatment groups and one control group. Data were collected using the Verbal Aggressive behaviour Scale. Three research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study at 0.5 level of significance. The hypotheses were tested using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). After exposure to intervention therapies, the results showed that there was significant difference in the post-test aggression scores of participants. Based on the findings it was concluded that both therapeutic approaches have shown positive outcomes in improving students' emotional regulation and social interactions. Recommendations were made that schools should implement both Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Social Learning Therapy as part of programmes aimed at reducing aggressive behaviour in adolescents. Since adolescents have varied psychological and emotional needs, interventions should be personalized to meet individual students' needs.

Keywords: Cognitive behaviour therapy, Adolescents, Social learning therapy, Aggressive behaviour.

Introduction

Aggression is a significant behavioural and emotional issue that common among teenagers. Adolescents afflicted with this “disease” may exhibit a consistent pattern of disruptive and aggressive conduct, as well as encounter difficulties adhering to regulations (Hinshaw & Lee, 2023). It is not unusual for teenagers to experience behavior-related issues at some point during their growth and maturation. Nevertheless, aggressive behaviour is classified as a conduct disorder when it persists over time, infringing upon the rights of others, deviating from recognised behavioural norms, and significantly disrupting the daily lives of the child and their family (Hinshaw & Lee, 2023; Goldberg, 2022).

The term "adolescence" is derived from the Latin word "adolescent," which signifies the process of growing or reaching maturity (Oladele, 1994; Martins, Carlson & Buskist, 2017). Psychologists have provided many definitions of adolescence. Adolescence is commonly described as the phase of life that bridges childhood and maturity. It is characterised by physical, mental, and social changes. This indicates that the transition encompasses both social and biological aspects. Adolescence refers to the period of time that spans from the onset of sexual maturation (puberty) to the attainment of maturity. It is a period of psychological development in which an individual acquires adult-like behaviour. Sacks (2023) defines adolescence as the period that starts when an individual has normal physiological puberty and ends when they have fully embraced an adult identity and behaviour. This developmental phase aligns approximately with the period spanning from 10 to 19 years of age, in accordance with the definition of adolescence provided by the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2013).

According to Martins, Carlson, and Buskist (2017), adolescence is defined as the period of time between the teenage years and the early twenties. Gutgesell and Payne (2014) describe adolescence as a lengthy stage of development that typically lasts around ten years, spanning from ages eleven to twenty-one. Additionally, it is observed that during adolescence, individuals undergo sequential phases of physiological maturation along with alterations in psychological and social capabilities. Acquiring appropriate emotions and managing them is crucial during adolescence. It is crucial to meet societal expectations and mitigate the negative impact of emotions on attitudes, habits,

behaviour, and physical health. Additionally, it is important to have emotional control. Control is adopting a reasonable mindset and suppressing socially inappropriate emotions when dealing with a social circumstance, rather than simply repressing them.

During adolescence, individuals acquire a clear understanding of the expected and inappropriate behaviours that are associated with their gender. Adolescents occasionally engage in misconduct for many causes. Perhaps, they perceive a need to establish their autonomy or they desire to challenge the boundaries imposed upon them. Adolescents may engage in misbehaviour due to internal anguish, such as anger, frustration, disappointment, worry, or hopelessness. Additionally, there are individuals whose conduct continually raises concerns among others. In such instances, the behaviour of adolescents is evidently beyond the spectrum of what is seen normal or acceptable. What is particularly concerning is that a significant number of these individuals display minimal remorse, sorrow, or comprehension of the harm and suffering caused by their actions (Pruitt, 2020).

When an individual reaches adolescence stage, he/she knows what type of behaviour is expected of him or her and those that are unacceptable. Adolescents however misbehave from time to time for a variety of reasons. Sometimes, adolescents misbehave because they are experiencing internal distress, anger, frustration, disappointment, anxiety, or hopelessness. In some cases, the adolescents' behaviour is clearly outside the range of what is considered normal or acceptable. Perhaps, most alarming is that many of them show little remorse, guilt, or understanding of the damage and pain inflicted on people by their behaviour (Pruitt, 2000).

School engagement involves students' active involvement in classroom tasks and school activities. School engagement also implies the rate at which parents show keen interest in ensuring that their children attend school punctually to prevent being delinquent. In fact, parents who fail to assist their children in their school work would expect a very poor academic achievement. Furthermore, some parents' apathy towards their children's education increases the rate of aggressive behaviour among students. It is obvious that some parents do not appreciate the value of education for their children because, for them education is not a priority.

Some teachers prepare inadequate lesson notes that do not sustain students' interest which result to poor students and teacher relationship. Nwankwo (2016) stressed that some teachers treat

students as if their psychological, emotional and social needs are identical. In the same vein, Makinde (2014) stated that if children are raised in a loving environment, their psychological, emotional and social potentials will develop well. In fact, understanding the individual differences in students depicts a teacher's high degree of professionalism.

Gender also plays a significant role in the rate of aggressiveness as boys and girls are involved as some of the students do not see the need for regular school attendance. In the United States of America, the male students are considered less likely to graduate than the females and the gap is 14% between male and females among African American students (Monrad, 2017). However, Gesinde (2004) stated that boys at any level of education exhibit aggressiveness more than the girls. In their submission, Nwankwo and Onyali's (2021) survey on truancy and dropping out of school revealed that in Nigeria, both gender exhibit similarities on aggressive behaviour rate. It is therefore obvious that male and female students engage in aggressiveness in that they share common interest.

Over the years, counsellors have used different counselling strategies to address adolescence aggressive behaviour (Oliha, 2010, Henry, 2007). However, adolescent aggressive behaviour could be better reduced through the use of social learning and cognitive behaviour therapies. For instance Cognitive Behavior Therapy (CBT) is a psychotherapy based on modifying everyday thoughts and behaviors, with the aim of positively influencing emotions. This same general approach developed out of behavior modification and cognitive therapy, and has become widely used to treat mental disorders. The therapeutic techniques vary according to the particular kind of client or issue, but commonly include keeping a diary of significant events and associated feelings, thoughts and behaviors; questioning and testing assumptions or habits of thoughts that might be unhelpful and unrealistic; gradually facing activities which may have been avoided; and trying out new ways of behaving and reacting. Relaxation and distraction techniques are also commonly included CBT and is widely accepted as an evidence-based, cost, effective psychotherapy for many disorders. The techniques are also commonly adopted for self-help manuals and increasingly self-help software packages (Norcross and Goldfried, 2005). Cognitive behavioral therapy interventions in high school would mainly be concerned with helping students realize three things: how their thought patterns affect their behavior; how they can take control of these thought patterns and how they can apply interventions to effect behavior change (Hall and Hughes, 1989). Cognitive

behaviour entails changing a perception from interpretation to a neutral or positive one, making it less stressful. This process is called reappraisal, rebelling, refraining and attitude adjustment (Serward, 2011). The cognitive behaviour strategies are designed to uncover dysfunctional and maladaptive thinking that often accompany psychological distress and challenges. These strategies are based on the belief that one's feelings are a direct result of one's thought.

On the other hand, Social Learning Theory (SLT) focused on observation, imitation and modelling (Bandura, 2020). The process involves communication, innovation, determination and perseverance. The techniques are designed to encourage interaction that enhances novel behaviour. It stresses the use of personal and interpersonal skills, to achieve good social skills that will enhance positive relationship among people. The goal of the intervention is to enable students change their attitude by watching models. Also initiating peers is significant in behaviour change as it helps to assist students with skills required for interpersonal relationship. Furthermore, it improves self-expression, respect for others, identify assertive and non-assertive behaviour, thus allowing the students to cope with the challenges of regular school attendance. In other words, what and how one thinks determine how that person feels. All behaviour whether deviant, adaptive or maladaptive, appropriate or inappropriate are learned and maintained according to the same principles (Okoli 2022). The goal of the interaction is to unlearn, improve and hopefully change maladaptive cognitions, thus allowing the client to live a far more productive and happy life. Therefore, this study is to investigate the effects of cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) and social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing Adolescents' aggressive behaviour in secondary schools in Oyo Town.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescents with behavioural disorder not only affect themselves but their families, schools and also the society at large. Increase in adolescents' behavioural disorder has led to a leap in chaos, disorderliness, destruction of lives and property, armed robbery, terrorist activities, kidnapping, oil bunkering, and many more evils. The Nigerian government established Remand Homes, Approved Schools and Juvenile Courts to address these behavioural disorders in adolescents but mere admission of the latter is not sufficient to reduce or eradicate the aggression. For adolescents with aggression to be helped, there is, the need to expose them to counselling interventions in order

for them to become responsible individuals to themselves and their parents, good students at school and worthy ambassadors of the nation as a whole Granero, Aymami, Go´mez-Pen˜ a, & Jaurrieta, 2017; Aderanti & Hassan, 2021).

Cognitive behavior therapy, which focuses on altering maladaptive thought patterns and behaviors, has been shown to address underlying cognitive distortions that contribute to aggression. By promoting self-regulation and enhancing coping strategies, CBT aims to reduce aggressive responses and improve interpersonal relationships (Beck & Dozois, 2018). Conversely, social learning therapy, which is based on the principles of observational learning, modeling, and reinforcement, seeks to teach and reinforce positive social behaviors while discouraging aggression (Bandura, 2020). Therefore, this study sets out to examine the effects of cognitive behaviour and social learning therapies in the treatment of aggression among adolescents in Secondary schools in Oyo Town.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effects of cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) and social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing adolescents’ aggressive behaviour in secondary schools. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. examine the effect of CBT in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.
2. Find out the effect of SLT in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.
3. examine the effect of gender on CBT and SLT in reducing aggressive behaviours among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.

Hypotheses

1. **There is no significant** treatment effect of Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) in reducing aggressive behaviour among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town
2. **There is no significant** treatment effect of Social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing aggressive behaviour among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town

3. **There is no significant** interaction effect of **gender on** CBT and SLT in reducing aggressive behaviour among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.

Methodology

The study adopted quasi-experimental research design. In the study, intact classes were assigned to the two therapies: cognitive behaviour, social learning and control group. This is because it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the students and assign them to groups. The study adopted a factorial research of 3 x 2 to test null hypotheses for the study. The first three factorial levels are the two experimental groups (Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Social Learning Therapy) and one control group. The second factorial level is gender occurring in either male (M) or female (F). In this study, only the two experimental groups received treatment while the control group did not. All the groups (experimental and control group) received pre-test and post-test before and after the lesson.

The population of this study comprised all public Senior Secondary School adolescents in Oyo Town. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 150 students from three senior secondary schools in the study area. Thus, through the technique adopted, the schools were assigned to experimental and control groups as follows: E₁ (Experimental group 1, cognitive behaviour); E₂ (Experimental group 2, social learning); and C₃ (Control group).

The Aggression Questionnaire (AQ). Was used to assess aggressive behaviour. It consists of 29 items and divided into four factors: Items 1-9 measure physical aggression, 10-14 is on verbal aggression, 15-21 for anger while 22-29 for hostility. It is important to note that the instrument had been widely used. For instance, in Nigeria, the scale has been used to test physical and verbal aggression among adolescent secondary schools in Oyo state of Nigeria. Again, the instrument has been used to evaluate the effects of some psychological variables on aggressive behavior of teachers in Nigeria Primary Schools. Reliability indices were between 0.67 and 0.71.

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction for permission from the Department of Educational Psychology, Emmanuel Alayande University of Education, Oyo. The researcher sought permission from Oyo State Teaching Service Commission. (TESCOM), Oyo Zonal office to carry out the work. The research instruments were administered to the respondents by the researcher with the aid of the research assistants recruited for the purpose of the study. The work was carried

out in three phases. Pre-intervention assessment, intervention and post intervention assessment. The data collected was analysed using inferential statistics of ANCOVA.

Results

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant treatment effect of Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Mean Achievement Scores of adolescents on Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school students in Oyo Town

Dependent Variable: Source	POST TEST Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	14042.094 ^a	2	7021.047	192.354	.000	.908
Intercept	503.461	1	503.461	13.793	.001	.261
PRETEST	9305.999	1	9305.999	254.954	.000	.867
GENDER	4353.471	1	4353.471	119.271	.000	.754
Error	1423.525	39	36.501			
Total	92266.000	42				
Corrected Total	15465.619	41				

Source: Field Study, 2025

The data in table 1 indicates an f-value of 119.271 and a significant p-value of .000. Since the p-value of .000 is lower than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of adolescents' cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary schools.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant treatment effect of Social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing aggressive behavior among secondary school adolescents.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Mean Achievement Scores of adolescents on Social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town.

Source	Type III Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	9691.345 ^a	2	4845.672	32.728	.000	.627
Intercept	361.938	1	361.938	2.445	.126	.059
PRETEST	8600.964	1	8600.964	58.092	.000	.598
GENDER	2.723	1	2.723	.018	.893	.000
Error	5774.274	39	148.058			
Total	92266.000	42				
Corrected Total	15465.619	41				

Source: Field Study, 2025

The data in table 2 indicates an f-value of .018 and significant p-value of .893. Since the p-value of .893 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of participants on Social learning therapy (SLT) in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescent students in Oyo Town.

Research Hypothesis 3: There is no significant interaction effect of gender on CBT and SLT in reducing aggressive behaviors.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Interaction Effect of Gender on Mean Achievement Scores of Adolescents Using CBT and SLT therapies in reducing aggressive behaviors.

Source	Type III Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	14174.314 ^a	4	3543.578	101.535	.000	.917
Intercept	307.545	1	307.545	8.812	.005	.192
GENDER	.947	1	.947	.027	.870	.001
PRETEST	7711.422	1	7711.422	220.957	.000	.857
GENDER*THERAPIES	4482.969	2	2241.484	64.226	.000	.776
Error	1291.306	37	34.900			
Total	92266.000	42				
Corrected Total	15465.619	41				

Source: Field Study. 2025

The data in table 3 indicates an f-value of 2241.484 and significant p-value of .000. Since the p-value of .000 is lesser than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, there is a significant interaction effect of treatment using CBT and SLT and gender on the mean achievement scores in reducing aggressive behaviors among secondary school adolescent students. Consequently, gender has a significant interaction effect on male and female students with CBT and SLT therapies

Discussion

The main objective of this study was to find out the effectiveness of cognitive behavior Therapy (CBT) in reducing aggressive behaviour among senior secondary students in Oyo Town. The use of psychotherapeutic therapy has been suggested by psychologists and guidance counsellors to treat some disorders. Cognitive behaviour therapy is one of those suggested treatment for aggressive behaviour. This treatment package was employed in this study to find out its effectiveness in reducing aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school adolescents in Oyo Town. The study found out that significant differences existed in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school adolescents in the treatment group. The calculated pre-treatment mean scores of cognitive behaviour therapy dropped significantly among senior secondary adolescents in the treatment group after the application of cognitive behaviour therapy (CBT). The findings further mirrored the observation of Shapiro (2019) that in her experiment, participants receiving Cognitive Behavioural Technique treatment experienced a complete and nearly immediate reduction in aggressive symptoms related to their traumatic memories while those in the control group showed no such change.

Hypothesis two revealed that Social learning counselling technique had significant effect on hostile aggressive behaviour of senior secondary school students in Oyo Town. This implies that when compared with their pre-test, the subjects exposed to social skill counselling technique shows a significant reduction in the post-test score which indicated significant effect of SSTCT on hostile aggressive behaviour of senior secondary school adolescents. This is supported by the study of Smokowski et al (2024) on School-Based Skills Training to Prevent Aggressive Behaviour and Peer Rejection in Childhood: Evaluating the Making Choices Programme. The study revealed that, minority children who received the making choices intervention of social skills training had lower

post-test ratings on overt (hostile) aggression than minority children who did not receive the intervention. This implied that, social skills training had significant effect in reducing hostile aggression in children.

Hypothesis three showed that **there is no significant** difference in the post-test scores in the dependent measures (aggressive behaviour). The statistical results showed that there was significant gender difference in the dependent measures of aggressive behaviour and of the participants' post-test scores. This is in line with study outcome of Nwolisa, Olusakin & Fashina (2019) who argued that the effect of both cognitive behavior therapy and modelling in alleviating aggressive behaviour in both male and female respondents could be due to the fact when real life models of which they identified themselves were discussed, they found out that if those people could become great in life, they too could equally achieve greatness if they could look beyond where were now and focus their attention on what they would like to become in the future. The way they previously had seen themselves and their situations gradually began to give way to more self-confident individual. It is essential to note that the knowledge and skills that individual possess play critical roles in what they choose to do and not to do. Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) and Social Learning Therapy are efficacious in the group management of psychosocial problems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, both Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) and Social Learning Therapy (SLT) have demonstrated significant effects on reducing aggression among adolescents in senior secondary school settings. The application of CBT in addressing cognitive distortions, maladaptive thought patterns, and emotional regulation has proven to be effective in reducing aggressive behaviors. CBT helps students identify and challenge negative thoughts and replace them with healthier, more adaptive thinking, leading to improved impulse control and conflict resolution skills. On the other hand, Social Learning Therapy emphasizes the importance of modeling appropriate behaviors and reinforcement, with an emphasis on observing and imitating positive behaviors. Through this approach, students can learn effective strategies for managing frustration, interacting with peers, and resolving conflicts without resorting to aggression. The results suggest that SLT's focus on observational learning and reinforcement encourages students to adopt pro-social behaviors and decreases instances of aggressive conduct.

Both therapeutic approaches have shown positive outcomes in improving students' emotional regulation and social interactions. However, the combination of both therapies could potentially have an even greater impact, as CBT addresses internal cognitive processes while SLT focuses on external social influences.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Schools should implement both Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Social Learning Therapy as part of therapeutic programmes aimed at reducing aggression in adolescents. Combining both methods could provide a more holistic approach to addressing the psychological and social factors contributing to aggressive behavior.
2. Since adolescents have varied psychological and emotional needs, interventions should be personalized to meet individual students' needs. Regular assessments and follow-ups are essential to evaluate progress and adjust interventions accordingly.
3. Teachers, school counsellors, and staff should receive training in CBT and SLT techniques so that they can implement these strategies in the classroom and school environment. This can help to reinforce positive behavior and provide immediate intervention when aggressive incidents arise.
4. Peer mediation programmes, where students are trained in conflict resolution and aggression management techniques, could serve as an additional tool to reduce aggression in the school setting. These programmes could be informed by both CBT and SLT principles to empower students to manage conflicts constructively.

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